

Synthesis of Some Fungitoxic 2-Thiadiazolyl-Quinazol-4-Ones

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Several 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles have been condensed with 3 : 1 : 4-benzoxazone to get 3-(5-substituted-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)-quinazol-4-ones. These compounds have been tested for their fungicidal properties against *A. niger*.

In view of the fact that a thiadiazole ring incorporates $> \text{N}-\overset{\text{I}}{\underset{\text{I}}{\text{C}}}-\text{S}$ linkage which is so characteristic toxophore for many species of fungi, and a quinazolone ring is of versatile biological interest as is apparent from its presence in antimalarial alkaloid febrifugine, and the use of several quinazolone compounds as bactericidal¹ and fungicidal² agents, it was anticipated that a combination of the two ring systems may yield compounds of enhanced fungitoxicity. With this aim the title compounds were synthesised and tested against *A. niger*.

EXPERIMENTAL

3 : 1 : 4-Benzoxazone was prepared according to the method of Zentmeyer and Wagner³. A mixture of formyl anthranilic acid (40 g.) and acetic anhydride (330 ml) was refluxed for 2 hrs in oil bath. After cooling the excess acetic anhydride was removed and the dark viscous liquid left in the flask was redistilled to give the product b.p. 122°. Zentmeyer and Wagner report same b.p.

2-Amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles were prepared according to the method of Mafii et al.^{4,5} by cyclisation of aroyl-thiosemicarbazides in presence of conc. H₂SO₄.

3-(5-substituted-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl) quinazol-4-ones : An equimolecular mixture of the required thiadiazole compound and the benzoxazone was heated on a water bath for 4-5 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled, washed several times with dil. HCl and water and finally recrystallised from aqueous alcohol. The compounds thus prepared are listed in Table I.

Evaluation of fungicidal activity : These compounds have been tested for their fungicidal action on *Aspergillus niger* by Agar-growth technique at two different concentrations namely, 1 : 10,000 and 1 : 100,000. The average percentage inhibition by various compounds is given in Table II.

TABLE I

Sl.No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Formula	% Sulphur		% Nitrogen	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	CH ₃	181	55	C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₄ OS	13.09	13.11	22.46	22.95
2.	C ₂ H ₅	340 ^d	51	C ₂₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ OS	12.41	12.30	21.36	21.70
3.	4-OH-C ₆ H ₄	138	36	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S	9.67	9.96	17.62	17.95
4.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	168	51	C ₁₆ H ₉ N ₅ O ₃ S	9.42	9.11	19.36	16.69
5.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	300	50	C ₁₆ H ₉ N ₄ SOCl	9.22	9.41	16.21	16.44
6.	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	144	63	C ₁₆ H ₉ N ₅ O ₃ S	9.17	9.11	19.27	19.69

d : decomposes

TABLE II

S.No*.	No. of Replications	Average percentage inhibition after 96 hrs. concentration used	
		1 : 10,000	1 : 100,000
1	3	37.4	26.3
2	3	32.5	20.6
3	3	24.8	16.5
4	3	34.2	21.7
5	3	33.2	19.1
6	3	35.3	20.4

* The S.No. of compounds corresponds to those recorded in Table I.

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